

Multi Stage Filter Using Enhanced Adaboost for Network Intrusion Detection

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Abstract: *Based on the analysis and distribution of network attacks in KDDCup99 dataset and real time traffic, this paper proposes a design of multi stage filter which is an efficient and effective approach in dealing with various categories of attacks in networks. The first stage of the filter is designed using Enhanced Adaboost with Decision tree algorithm to detect the frequent attacks occurs in the network and the second stage of the filter is designed using enhanced Adaboost with Naïve Byes algorithm to detect the moderate attacks occurs in the network. The final stage of the filter is used to detect the infrequent attack which is designed using the enhanced Adaboost algorithm with Naïve Bayes as a base learner. Performance of this design is tested with the KDDCup99 dataset and is shown to have high detection rate with low false alarm rates.*

Keywords: Enhanced Adaboost, multi stage filter, decision tree, Naive Bayes classification, detection rate, false alarm rate.

1. Introduction

With the development of the Internet, web applications are becoming increasingly popular and it plays an important role in human life. Consequently, the various Internet resources are becoming the major targets of many attacks. Due to the growing number of users, networking components and the applications in the Internet, it is mandatory that development of new techniques that can secure and protect the Internet resources against the various attacks. These issues have given rise to a research on Network Intrusion Detection systems.

The intrusion detection is a vital part of network security. Intrusion detection is the detection of user behaviors in the network that deviates from the organizations network security policy. The goals of network intrusion detection are to identify, categorize and possibly respond to malicious or suspicious activities [1, 2]. There are basically two types of intrusion detection systems namely anomaly detection and misuse detection. Anomaly detection system first learns normal system activities and then alerts all system events that deviate from the learned model and the misuse detection uses the signature of attacks to detect intrusions by modeling attacks.

1.1. Related work

The field of network intrusion detection and network security has been around since late 1990s. Since then, a number of frameworks and methodologies have been proposed and many tools have been built to detect network intrusion. Various methodologies such as rule based

algorithm, classification, clustering, genetic algorithms, support vector machines, hybrid classification and others have been used to detect network intrusions. In this section, we briefly discuss few of these methodologies and frameworks.

Weiming Hu et. al., [3] have proposed an Adaboost based algorithm for network intrusion detection. The AdaBoost algorithm is one of the most popular machine learning algorithms and it corrects the misclassifications made by weak classifiers. The authors in [3] used decision stump as a weak classifier. The decision rules are provided for both categorical and continuous features and some provision was made for handling the overfitting.

N.B.Amor et. al, [4] discuss the use of Decision tree and Naïve Bayes classifiers for network intrusion detection. The decision trees select the best features for each decision node during the construction of the tree based on some well defined criteria. Decision trees generally have very high speed of operation and high attack detection accuracy. The Naïve Bayes classifiers make strict independence assumption between the features in an observation resulting in lower attack detection accuracy when the features are correlated, which is often the case for intrusion detection.

Dewan Md. Farid et. al., [5] constructed an adaptive intrusion detection system by combining Naïve Bayes and Decision tree algorithms. The various issues of intrusion detection system are addressed in this model and its performance is better in terms of attack detection rate and false positive rate with limited computational resources.

Natesan et. al, [6] proposed the use of multiple base learners with Adaboost algorithm. The Decision tree algorithm, Naïve Bayes and Bayes Net are used as base learners and it is also combined in three different ways with Adaboost and its performance is better in terms of Attack detection rate and false alarm rate. Xiang et al [7] proposed multiple-level Hybrid Classifier (MLHC), which involved both the supervised classification stages and unsupervised Bayesian clustering to detect intrusions. There are four classification stages in hybrid classifier which uses Bayesian clustering and decision tree technologies. Gupta et al [8] proposed a Layered approach using Conditional Random Fields (CRFs), where it is considered that the attack categories as layers and different features were selected for each layer.

Chin khor et al [9] proposed a cascaded classifier approach in which they divided the training set in to non-rare attack categories and rare attack categories and trained the classifiers using these two training datasets. The methodologies used in the cascaded classifier approach were Bayes net and C4.5 decision tree. Natesan et. al [10] proposed a two stage filter in which the Adaboost with Decision tree methodology is used in the first stage and the Adaboost with Bayes Net methodology is used in the second stage of the filter. In our work, we define three stage filters, first stage is to filter the DoS attacks which occur frequently in the network and the second stage is to filter Probe attacks which occur moderately in the network. The third stage of the filter is used to filter the R2L and U2R attacks which occur rarely in the network. This approach improves the detection rate of Probe attacks and also the detection of novel attacks improved.

1.2. Dataset Analysis

Under the sponsorship of Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) and Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), MIT Lincoln laboratory has collected and distributed the datasets for the evaluation of researches in computer network intrusion detection systems. The KDDCup99 dataset is subsets of the DARPA benchmark dataset [11].

KDDCup99 training dataset is about four giga bytes of compressed binary TCP dump data from seven weeks of network traffic, processed into about five million connections record each with about 100 bytes. The two weeks of test data have around two million connection records. Each KDDCup'99 training connection record contains 41 features and is labeled as either normal or an attack, with exactly one specific attack type [11].

There are about 494,020 records in KDDCup'99 training set and 311,029 records in the KDDCup'99 test set. The various attack types in the datasets are grouped into attack categories in order to combine similar attack types into a single category which could improve the detection rate. The training set consists of 24 attack types and the test set contains 38 attack types in which 14 attack types are novel attacks. All the attacks in the dataset fall into four major categories, namely, *Denial of Service (Dos)*, *Probing (Probe)*, *Remote to Local (R2L)* and *User to Root (U2R)*. Table.1 shows the attacks in the KDDCup'99 training set and the additional attacks present in the KDDCup'99 test set.

Table 1: Attacks present in the KDDCup'99 Datasets

Attack Category	Attacks in KDDCup'99 Training set	Additional attacks in KDDCup'99 Test set
Dos	back, neptune, smurf, teardrop, land, pod.	apache2, mailbomb, processtable.
Probe	satan, portsweep, ipsweep, nmap.	mscan, saint.
R2L	warezmaster, warezclient, ftpwrite, guesspassword, imap, multihop, phf, spy	sendmail, named, snmpgetattack, snmpguess, xlock, xsnoop, worm.
U2R	rootkit, bufferoverflow, loadmodule, perl.	httptunnel, ps, sqlattack, xterm

Table.2 and Table.3 shows the number of records for each attack category in the training and testing datasets respectively.

Table 2: Number of samples in the KDDCup'99 Training set and distribution of attacks

Attack Category	Number of samples	Distribution of Attacks in %
Normal	97,277	19.6909
Dos	391,458	79.2393
Probe	4,107	0.8313
R2L	1,126	0.2279
U2R	52	0.0105
Total	494,020	100

Table 3: Number of samples in the KDDCup'99 Test set and distribution of attacks

Attack Category	Number of samples	Distribution of Attacks in %
Normal	60,593	19.4814
Dos	229,853	73.9008
Probe	4,166	1.3394
R2L	16,189	5.2049
U2R	228	0.0733
Total	311,029	100

The percentage of distribution of attacks is not uniform in the training set and the test set. Also, the probability of distribution of attacks in the test set is different from training set. For example, there are about only 0.2% of R2L attacks in the training set but it is about 5.2% in the test set. This is one of the challenging tasks in the classification of attacks.

2. Methodology in building IDS

This section will give a detailed description about the Rough set theory which is used to extract the relevant features for detecting the specific category of attacks from the generic 41 features present in the KDDCup99 dataset. With the selected features, the enhanced Adaboost algorithm can achieve the low false alarm rate with high attack detection rate. This section also discuss about the enhanced Adaboost algorithm.

2.1. Rough set theory

Z.Pawlak introduced the Rough set theory in the early 1980s, is an extension of set theory for study of the intelligent systems characterized by insufficient and incomplete information [12]. Recently, rough set theory has attracted a lot of attention and has been applied in the areas of patterns extraction, text classification, machine learning, information retrieval and etc. [13-15].

We present an overview of rough set theory and the notations used in this paper. In rough set theory, an information system, which is also called a decision table, is defined as $S = \{U, A, V, f\}$, where $U = \{U_1, U_2, \dots, U_m\}$ is a non-empty, finite set of objects called universe. $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ is a non-empty, finite set of attributes. Here, m is the no.of objects and n is the number of attributions. It includes two non-intersect subsets: one is condition attributes subset C and another is decision attributes subset D , namely $A = C \cup D$, $C \cap D = \Phi$. $V = \bigcup_{a \in A} V_a$ ($a \in A$) is a set of values of attributes in A , V_a is called the domain of a .

$F: U \times A \rightarrow V_a$ is an information function, for any

$$a \in A, x \in U, f(x, a) \in V_a$$

The reduction of attributes means to find the minimum condition attribution subset whose classification quality is identical to the original condition attribution set.

Suppose U is the universe R is a group of equivalence relation, $r \in R$, if $U / \text{IND}(R) = U / \text{IND}(R-r)$, then we say r can be deducted from R . If every attribution in $P = R - \{r\}$ cannot be deducted, then we say P is a reduction of R .

2.2. Enhanced Adaboost Algorithm

AdaBoost is a fast machine learning algorithm, can be used in conjunction with many other learning algorithms to improve their performance. It calls a weak classifier repeatedly in a series of rounds. In each round of operation the classification error is calculated for various categories of attacks. The reweight is calculated and assigned to the instances. The pseudo code of our Enhanced Adaboost algorithm is given.

Input: D , a set of d class-labeled, n training network connections

k , the number of rounds, apply a classification learning scheme.

Output: An IDS model.

Steps:

- (1) Split the training dataset in to three datasets D_1 , D_2 and D_3
- (2) Extract the relevant features by applying Rough set
- (3) Initialize the weight of each network connection in D_x to $1/d$; x is the number of

Splits,

- (4) For $x=1$ to 3 do
- (5) For $i = 1$ to k do
- (6) Sample D_i with replacement according to the network connection weights to obtain D_s ;
- (7) Use training set D_s to derive a model, M_i ;
- (8) Calculate error (M_i), the error rate of the model M_i
- (9) if $error(M_i) > 0.5$ then
- (10) Reinitialize the weights to $1/d$
- (11) Go back to step 5 and try again;
- (12) End if
- (13) For each network connection in D_s that was correctly classified
Do
- (14) Update the weight of the network connection by
Error (M_i) = (1-Error (M_i));
- (15) Normalize the weight of each network connection
- (16) End for
- (17) End for

The Enhanced Adaboost algorithm uses C4.5 Decision tree and Naïve Bayes classification algorithms as its base learner.

3. Experiments

The various stages involved in our experiments are: splitting the training dataset, filter design and feature selection, training the filter and testing the model using KDDCup99 test set.

3.1 Splitting the training dataset

The KDDCup99 training dataset is split in to three training datasets. The first one consisted of records of Normal, DoS attack categories and the second one consisted of Normal, Probe attack categories. The third split consisted of records of Normal, R2L and U2R attack categories.

3.2 Filter design and Feature selection

The large number of features in the KDDCup99 dataset increases the computational and space cost, besides the redundant characteristics of the attributes make the attack detection accuracy dropped. Hence, to reduce the cost involved in computation and storage, rough set based feature selection was applied to select features that were relevant to detect the frequent attacks, moderate attacks and infrequent attacks in the KDDCup99 Training set. We have proposed a multi stage filter which consists of three stages as shown in Figure.1, the first stage is used to filter the DoS attacks and the second stage is for filtering Probe attacks in the network. The final stage is used to filter the R2L and U2R attacks. The proposed method is called a multi stage filter with Adaboost.

Figure .1: Block Diagram of Multi Stage filter

3.2.1 DoS attacks detection stage

This stage of the filter is aimed to detect Dos attacks which occur frequently in the network. In Dos attacks the attacker makes some computing or memory resources too busy or too full to handle legitimate requests or denies legitimate users access to a machine. The selected features to detect the DoS attacks are shown in Table.4.

Table. 4: Features selected for DoS attacks detection stage

Feature Number	Feature Name	Description
1	Duration	Length of the connection in seconds
2	protocol_type	Type of the protocol used. For eg. TCP
3	Service	Network service on the destination like HTTP, Telnet.
4	Flag	Normal or error status of the network connection.
5	src_bytes	Number of data bytes from source to destination.
6	dst_bytes	Number of data bytes from destination to source.
23	Count	Number of connections to the same host as the current connection in the past two seconds.
25	serror_rate	Percentage of connections that have "SYN" errors.
27	rerror_rate	Percentage of connections that have "REJ" errors.
30	diff_srv_rate	Percentage of connections that have same services.
32	dst_host_count	Count for destination host.
33	dst_host_srv_count	srv_count for destination host
34	dst_host_same_srv_rate	same_srv_rate for destination host
35	dst_host_diff_srv_rate	diff_srv_rate for destination host.
39	dst_host_srv_serror_rate	srv_serror_rate for destination host.

3.2.2 Probe attacks detection stage

This stage of the filter is aimed to detect Probe attacks which happen moderately in the network. Probe attacks scan a network to gather information or to find known vulnerabilities. An intruder with a map of machines and services that are available on a network can use the information to look for exploits. The selected features to detect the Probe attacks are shown in Table.5.

Table. 5: Features selected for Probe attacks detection stage

Feature Number	Feature Name	Description
1	Duration	Length of the connection in seconds
2	protocol_type	Type of the protocol used. For eg. TCP
3	Service	Network service on the destination like HTTP,

		Telnet.
5	src_bytes	Number of data bytes from source to destination.
6	dst_bytes	Number of data bytes from destination to source.
19	num_access_files	Number of operations on access control files
20	number_outbound_cmds	Number of outbound commands in an ftp session
23	Count	Number of connections to the same host as the current connection in the past two seconds.
25	serror_rate	Percentage of connections that have “SYN” errors.
27	rerror_rate	Percentage of connections that have “REJ” errors.
30	diff_srv_rate	Percentage of connections that have same services.
32	dst_host_count	Count for destination host.

3.2.3 R2L and U2R attacks detection stage

This stage of the filter is aimed to detect R2L and U2R attacks which happen rarely in the network. Remote to User (R2L) is an attack that a remote user gains access of a local user/account by sending packets to a machine over a network communication. User to Root (U2R) is an attack that an intruder begins with the access of a normal user account and then becomes a root-user by exploiting various vulnerabilities of the system. The selected features to detect the R2L and U2R attacks are shown in Table. 6.

Table. 6: Features selected for R2L and U2R attacks detection stage

Feature Number	Feature Name	Description
1	Duration	Length of the connection in seconds
2	protocol_type	Type of the protocol used. For eg. TCP
3	Service	Network service on the destination like HTTP, Telnet.
4	Flag	Normal or error status of the network connection.
5	src_bytes	Number of data bytes from source to destination
6	dst_bytes	Number of data bytes from destination to source.
10	Hot	Number of “hot” indicators.
11	num_failed_logins	Number of failed login attempts.
12	logged-in	1 if successfully logged in; 0 otherwise.
13	num_compromised	Number of compromised conditions.
14	root_shell	1 if root shell is obtained; 0 otherwise.
16	num_root	Number of “root” access.
17	num_file_creations	Number of file creation operations.
18	num_shells	Number of shell prompts.
19	num_access_files	Number of operations on access control files.
21	is_host_login	1 if the login belongs to “hot” list; 0 otherwise.

22	is_guest_login	1 if the login is a guest login; 0 otherwise.
23	Count	Number of connections to the same host as the current connection in the past two seconds
25	serror_rate	Percentage of connections that have “SYN” errors.
27	rerror_rate	Percentage of connections that have “REJ” errors.
30	diff_srv_rate	Percentage of connections that have same services.
32	dst_host_count	Count for destination host.
35	dst_host_diff_srv_rate	diff_srv_rate for destination host.
39	dst_host_srv_serror_rate	srv_serror_rate for destination host.

3.3 Training and Testing the Model

The multi stage filter is constructed using the selected features in Tables. 4,5 & 6. There are 15 features selected for the first stage of the filter which is used for detecting the DoS attacks which occurs frequently in the network and 12 features selected for the construction of the second stage of the filter which is used to filter out the Probe attacks which occurs moderately in the network. The third stage of the filter is constructed to filter out the R2L and U2R attacks which occur rarely in the network. There are 24 features selected for this stage to filter out the R2L and U2R attacks. The learning ability of any classification algorithm is dependent on the characteristics of the connections in the training data set.

The Enhanced Adaboost with Decision tree algorithm is used in constructing the first stage of the filter and it is trained with the training set which consists of Normal and DoS attack categories. The second stage of the filter is constructed by using the Enhanced Adaboost with Naïve Bayes classification algorithm as its base learner. The training dataset which consists of Normal and Probe attack categories is used in training the second stage of the filter. The third stage of the filter is also constructed by using the Enhanced Adaboost with Naïve Bayes classification algorithm as its base learner. The training dataset which consists of Normal, R2L and U2R attack categories is used in training the third stage of the filter. The trained model is tested using the KDDCup99 test set.

4. Experiments and Results

For our experiments we use the benchmark KDDCup99 dataset, in which each record represents a separate connection and hence each connection between the two IP addresses is considered to be independent of any other connection. We use the Weka tool to implement the Enhanced Adaboost algorithm and to perform classification with Decision Trees and naïve Bayesian classification.

4.1 Performance Measures

In machine learning and data mining algorithms, many different metrics are used to evaluate the classification models. We employed two performance measures: Attack detection rate and false alarm rate. These two measures are calculated by using a confusion matrix.

Confusion matrix is a two dimensional matrix representation of the classification results. The upper left cell in the matrix denotes the number of connections classified as Normal while they actually were Normal (i.e. TP), and the lower right cell in the matrix denotes the number of connections classified as Attack while they actually were Attack (i.e. TN). The other two cells (lower left cell and the upper right cell) denote the number of connections misclassified. Specifically, the lower left cell in the matrix denoting the number of connections classified as Normal while they actually were Attack (i.e. FN), and the upper right cell denoting the number of connections classified as Attack while they actually were Normal (i.e. FP).

	Classified as Normal	Classified as Attack
Normal	TP	FP
Attack	FN	TN

Attack Detection Rate (ADR): It is the ratio between total numbers of attacks detected by the system to the total number of attacks present in the dataset.

$$\text{Attack Detection Rate} = \frac{\text{Total detected attacks}}{\text{Total attacks}} * 100 \tag{1}$$

False Alarm Rate (FAR): It is the ratio between total numbers of misclassified instances to the total number of normal instances.

$$\text{False Alarm Rate} = \frac{\text{Total misclassified instances}}{\text{Total normal instances}} * 100 \tag{2}$$

4.2 Detecting the DoS attacks

We conducted two sets of experiments. In the first experiment, we considered all the 41 features of the dataset and examined the detection rate of the DoS attacks which occurs frequently in the network. Initially the Decision Tree is constructed and then to improve its classification accuracy the enhanced Adaboost algorithm is used. We perform the same experiment with the 15 features selected as in Table. 4 by using Enhanced Adaboost with Decision Tree as its base learner. The experimental results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: The attack detection rate of first stage of the filter

No. of features	% of detection rate	Training Time(sec)	Test Time(sec)
41	97.8	9.7	0.43
15	98.9	6.2	0.26

The system takes only 6.2 sec for its training when 15 features considered. Also it takes only 0.26 sec for the testing of the incoming network connection.

4.3 Detecting the Probe attacks

We conducted two sets of experiments. In the first experiment, we considered all the 41 features of the dataset and examined the detection rate of Probe attacks which happened moderately in the network. Initially the Naïve Bayes classification algorithm is chosen and then to improve its classification accuracy the enhanced Adaboost algorithm is used. We perform the same experiment with the 12 features selected as in Table.5 by using Enhanced Adaboost with Naïve Bayes as its base learner. The experimental results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: The attack detection rate of second stage of the filter

No. of features	% of detection rate	Training Time(sec)	Test Time(sec)
41	92.3	6.9	0.36
12	93.8	2.7	0.17

The system takes only 2.7 sec for its training when 12 features considered. Also it takes only 0.17 sec for the testing of the incoming network connection.

4.4 Detecting the R2L and U2R attacks

To detect the infrequent attacks, initially we conducted an experiment by considering all the 41 features. The Naïve Bayes algorithm is used as a base learner with the enhanced Adaboost algorithm. We perform the same experiment with 24 features which are relevant to detect infrequent attacks and the results are shown in Table 9. The training time and the testing time decreases marginally with the selected 24 features and there is a slight increase in the detection rate of attacks.

Table 9: The attack detection rate of third stage of the filter

No. of features	Attacks category	% of detection rate	Training Time(sec)	Test Time(sec)
41	Normal	98.8	14.7	0.83
	R2L	44.7		
	U2R	82.6		
24	Normal	99.3	11.2	0.62
	R2L	49.8		
	U2R	87.6		

The false alarm rate of this multi stage filter is found to be 1.97 % which is less as compared with the two stage filter [10].

4.5 System performance on Novel attacks

The KDDCup99 test dataset contains some specific type of new attacks that did not present in the KDDCup99 training dataset and this makes the classification task is more challenging. There are about 24 types of attacks in the training set and 14 types of additional novel attacks present in the test dataset as shown in the Table. 1. The network domain experts and intrusion detection system experts suggested that most of these attacks are slight variants of known attacks which are present in training set and the “patterns” of known attacks can be sufficient to detect the novel attacks. We conducted an experiment to test the performance of our system on novel attacks with the selected features and the results are shown in Table.10.

Table 10: Detection rate on Novel attacks

Attacks Category	Attacks Name	Number of attack connections in KDDCup99 test set	Number of attacks detected
Dos	apache2	794	575
	mailbomb	5,000	4,569
	process table	759	613
Probe	mscan	1,053	989
	saint	736	736
U2R	httptunnel	158	121
	ps	16	11
	sqlattack	2	1
	xterm	13	10
R2L	sendmail	17	12
	named	17	5
	snmpgetattack	7,741	3,865
	snmpguess	2,406	1,986
	xlock	9	2
	xsnoop	4	1
	worm	2	0
Total		18,729	13,496(72.1%)

The performance of our multi stage filter with Adaboost on novel attacks is remarkably high (an increase of 32.5%) as compared with the work in [19].

4.5 Comparisons of detection rate with different algorithms

The detection rate of our algorithm is compared with existing work as shown in Table. 11, which is tested on the benchmark KDDCup’99 dataset. The performance of our proposed two stage filter was comparatively better than existing work in detecting the DoS, R2L and U2R attacks (DoS - 98.8%, R2L - 49.8% and U2R - 87.6%). Hence, it should be considered for the building of IDS.

Table 11: Comparison with other algorithms

Name of the method	% of Detection rate				
	Normal	DoS	Probe	R2L	U2R
Cascaded classifier using J48-BN [9]	97.4	97.8	73.3	48.2	87.3
Multi layered hybrid classifier [7]	96.8	98.6	93.4	46.9	71.4
KDD'99 Winner[21]	99.5	97.1	83.3	8.4	13.2
Layered approach using CRFs[8]	N/A	97.4	98.62	29.6	86.3
Two stage filter using enhanced Adaboost [10]	99.2	98.7	92.4	49.5	87.5
Proposed Multi stage filter using enhanced Adaboost	98.8	98.9	93.8	49.8	87.6

5. Conclusion and Future work

We have proposed the Rough set theory for extracting relevant features and the Enhanced Adaboost algorithm for detecting the network intrusion. The experiment is conducted with all 41 features and with the selected features. The attacks detection rate is increased considerably with the selected features and the computational cost falls drastically. The various issues of intrusion detection system such as attack detection rate, false alarm rate and computational time for building robust, scalable and efficient system are addressed. It is important to have very quick attack detection with higher detection rate. The experiment result shows that the Rough set theory with enhanced Adaboost algorithm has quick attack detection with a high detection rate.

The areas for future research include the considering use of multi core processors in which each stage of the filter is configured to individual core of the processor which will improve the utilization of the processor and also the attraction detection time.

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